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Abstract

This article discusses the advantages of the production and use of phosphorus fertilizers in agriculture in Kazakhstan. The production of phosphoric mineral fertilizer is closely related to the development of phosphoric and phosphoric acid technology. For the production of phosphorus fertilizers, phosphorus - containing ores are used - natural deposits of phosphorites and apatites.

Keywords: phosphate ore, zhelvak phosphorites, phosphorus, apatite, phosphorus fertilizer.

Introduction

The correct determination of the phosphorus content of soil and plants is very important for agricultural science and practice. Phosphorus is involved in a number of processes that determine the growth, development and productivity of a plant: the formation of the cell nucleus and cell reproduction, the synthesis of lipids and special proteins, the transfer of hereditary properties, respiration and photosynthesis, the transfer of energy from energy-rich compounds to the poor, etc. Phosphorus as an indicator of human activity is known to be unique in its sensitivity and

stability. Its content in the soil is of great interest to archaeologists, providing them with information about the type and intensity of human activity. Measuring the total phosphorus content gives a more quantitative result than mobile phosphorus and represents the best indicator of changes caused by human activity [1,2].

Oolites are found in ores in the Karatau Basin. They form mineral formations in the form of balls or ellipsoids, the size of which ranges from several micrometers to 15-25 mm, and ooliths, the size of which is more than 2.0-5.0 mm, are called pizolites.

(A)

(B)

Figure 1. The structure of the oolith (A) and the appearance of the pizolite (B)

They have a concentric-shell, sometimes radial-ray structure. They can form large brides. In caves, sometimes very large ooliths are formed - cave pearls [3,4]. They can consist of calcium carbonate, iron and manganese oxides, and other minerals. Some oolites are found in the form of iron ore (pea ore) [5].

Oolite-micro-granular phosphorus (Karatau Basin, Kazakhstan) consists of round phosphate grains and ooliths (globular and ellipsoidal aggregates) with a size of 0.07-0.30 mm and a content of 20.0-35.0% P_2O_5 . Karatau phosphorites are difficult to enrich, so ores containing at least 24.5% P_2O_5 are treated with acid for Soluble Fertilizers; another area of use is electrothermal reduction by obtaining yellow phosphorus.

Zhelvak phosphorites are found in size from 0.03-0.05 to 15-30 cm, and more than 6.0-12.0% are in the form of P_2O_5 phosphate nodes (zhelvak) nodes. By screening and washing, a concentrate is obtained from

them (from 16-18 to 22-23% P_2O_5), the flotation of which can slightly increase the phosphorus content. If the main additive in such concentrates is quartz, they can be processed into soluble fertilizers (Chilisai deposit, Kazakhstan). Due to the high content of Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 , concentrates from phosphorites of the largest deposits of this type (Vyatka-Kama, Yegoryevskoye) are unsuitable for acid processing.

World reserves phosphorus 42.8 billion tones (1984). Phosphorus reserves in the USSR amounted to 968.8 million tons (P_2O_5 ; 1984), which was 53% of the total explored reserves of phosphate ores (the rest are apatite ores); the share of phosphorites in phosphate production is significantly lower (about 27%; 1984). The largest resources of phosphorites include the United States, Morocco and other northern countries. Africa and the Middle East, as well as Peru - in these countries, the reserves of phosphate raw materials are exclusively phosphorus.

Apatite is found in the ores of the Zhambyl phosphate deposit. The chemical formula of apatite is $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH},\text{F},\text{Cl})_2$. Considered a group of minerals of the phosphate class, which is the main component of phosphorus-rich apatite ores. Therefore, it is called agronomic ores [6]. There are minerals containing in variable quantities fluorine, chlorine, OH - or more precisely, the common name of a number of related minerals of the apatite group with the general formula $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{F},\text{OH},\text{Cl})$.

It is calcium phosphoric acid, but its appearance is so diverse and striking that it is not for nothing that old mineralogists called it apatite, which means "deceiver" in Greek: these are transparent crystals, they resemble beryl or even quartz, then they are dense masses that do not differ from ordinary limestone, then they are radial rays balls, the rock is granular and shiny, like coarse-grained marble.

Most of the phosphate ore produced at the Zhambyl fasfor plant (80-90%) is used to obtain various phosphorous fertilizers. Phosphorus is necessary for the normal growth of plants. Accumulating in biomass, phosphorus disappears from the soil. Every year, the world's products, along with the nitrogen and potassium contained in the soil, drain several million tons of phosphorus from the arable land, so it is necessary to restore its resources in the fertile layer. In ancient times, people fertilized the soil with manure, bones. The first artificial phosphorus fertilizer it is considered superphosphate. In England, lauz received in 1839, and in 1842 its first industrial production was organized. The first enterprise for the production of superphosphate in Russia appeared in 1868. Now it is obtained by treating apatite with sulfuric acid:

Indirectly obtained calcium sulfate is not released. For the production of fertilizers containing only one phosphorus, it is reduced and more complex fertilizers with two or three nutrients are produced. Most of the phosphorus fertilizers produced in Russia are ammophos, diamphos and azofoska. The annual world production of phosphorus fertilizers at the beginning of the 21st century amounted to 41 million tones and the total number of all fertilizers is 190 million tons. The main producers of phosphorus fertilizers are Morocco,

the United States and Russia, and the main consumers are the countries of Asia, Latin America and Western Europe [7].

The cheapest phosphorus fertilizer is finely ground phosphorite-phosphorite flour. Phosphorus is present in the form of calcium phosphate $\text{Ca}_3(\text{RO}_4)_2$, which is insoluble in water. Therefore, phosphorites are not absorbed by all plants and in all soils. The bulk of the extracted phosphorus ores are processed by chemical methods into substances available to all plants in any soil. These are water-soluble calcium phosphates:

Double superphosphate (similar in color and appearance to ordinary superphosphate – a gray fine-grained powder). A more valuable product is double superphosphate, since it contains three times the mass of phosphorus, which is obtained by treating apatite with phosphoric acid:

Compared to simple superphosphate, it does not contain Saso4 and is a fairly concentrated fertilizer (up to 50% P_2O_5 in composition). Precipitate - contains 35-40% P_2O_5 .

It is obtained by neutralizing phosphoric acid with a solution of calcium hydroxide:

It is used in acidic soils. Ammophos is a complex fertilizer containing nitrogen (up to 15% N) and phosphorus (up to 58% P_2O_5) in the form of $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$. It is obtained by neutralizing phosphoric acid with ammonia. In the past, for more than 100 years, simple superphosphate, which is formed when sulfuric acid acts on natural calcium phosphate, has been widely used as a phosphorus fertilizer:

In this case, sulfuric acid reacts relatively less with calcium phosphate than to obtain phosphoric acid from it. A mixture of calcium dihydrophosphate and calcium sulfate is obtained. It is a fertilizer with a mass fraction of P_2O_5 of no more than 20%. Now ordinary superphosphate is produced in relatively small quantities in previously built plants. As an example, Table 1 presents the types of phosphorus-containing fertilizers at the phosphorus plant of Zhana Zhambyl [8].

Table 1.

Types of phosphorus-containing fertilizers at the phosphorus plant of Zhana Zhambyl

Fertilizer name	Chemical composition
<i>Simple</i>	
Double superphosphate	$\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$
Simple superphosphate	$\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 + 2\text{CaSO}_4$
Phosphorite flour	$\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$
Bone meal	$\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$
Prescipitate	$\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Slag of open-hearth furnaces	<i>Complex composition.</i> Contains P, Ca, Si, C, Fe and other elements
<i>Complex</i>	
Ammophos	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4 + \text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$
Diammonium phosphate	$\text{N}(18\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(46\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,8\%)$
Sulfoammophos	$\text{N}(14\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(34\%) + \text{S}(8\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,0\%)$
APF	$\text{N}(16\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(20\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,5\%)$
Nitroammophosphate	$\text{N}(21\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(23\%+14\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,0\%)$
Azoprecipitate	$\text{N}(26\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(13\%+6\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,0\%)$
Low-acid nitrogen-phosphorus fertilizer	$\text{N}(31\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(5\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(0,5\%)$
Nitrogen phosphate	$\text{N}(33\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(5\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,0\%)$
Ammophoska	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4 + \text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 + \text{KCl}$
Azofoska	$\text{N}(16\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(16\%) + \text{K}_2\text{O}(16\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,0\%)$
Azofoska with sulfur	$\text{N}(27\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(6\%) + \text{K}_2\text{O}(6\%) + \text{S}(2\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,0\%)$
NPK	$\text{N}(13\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(19\%) + \text{K}_2\text{O}(19\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,5\%)$
Diammophoska	$\text{N}(10\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(26\%) + \text{K}_2\text{O}(26\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(1,5\%)$
Nitroammophos	$\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 + \text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$
Liquid complex fertilizer (LCF)	$\text{N}(11\%) + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5(37\%) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(51,6\%)$

The use of phosphorus fertilizers in agriculture.

Agricultural crops produce about two-thirds of the phosphorus extracted from the soil by the crop. These losses are also restored by applying mineral fertilizers to the soil.

The required composition of the fertilizer used and its effectiveness depend on the characteristics of the soil, for example, pH, but the solubility of phosphate fertilizers determines the time of its absorption by plants and the proportion of phosphorus absorbed, which is usually small and is about 20%.

Double superphosphate is a granular mineral phosphorus fertilizer. Superphosphate is obtained by decomposing apatite concentrate with phosphoric acid, the fertilizer does not contain sulfur.

The main composition of superphosphate includes 43% phosphorus, including up to 6.5% in the form of free phosphoric acid. Fertilizer is used in any soil mainly for the main application, it can be used for fertilizer. Especially effective on alkaline and neutral soils. Doses of introduction of double superphosphate when used in agriculture are established by the agrochemical service, taking into account the provision of the soil with nutrient elements and biological characteristics of crops.

Double superphosphate has good physico-chemical properties, is widely used as a phosphorus component in the preparation of a sludge mixture, as well as as a chemical raw material in industry.

Table 2.

Physico-chemical composition of double superphosphate at the phosphorus plant of Zhanazhambyl

Name of indicators	Normal
Mass fraction of absorbable phosphates P_2O_5 , %	43
Mass fraction of free acid H_3PO_4 , %	6,5
Mass fraction of water, %	3
Granulometric composition:	
- Less than 1 mm, %	3
- From 1 to 4 mm, %	90
- Less than 6 mm, %	100
Static strength of granules, MPA (kgf/cm ²)	3,0 (30)
Creeps, %	100

Superphosphate is simple-a granular phosphorus fertilizer containing 26% water-soluble phosphorus. Superphosphate contains 6% nitrogen, 10% sulfur, 17% calcium, 0.5% magnesium. 26% to 2.5% of the phosphorus in superphosphate is in the form of free phosphoric acid.

Granulation improves the consumer properties of the fertilizer, which is very important when using superphosphate on acidic soils rich in one and a half oxides, which bind phosphorus to insoluble and

difficult for plants to reach iron and aluminum phosphates. On slightly acidic and neutral soils, calcium phosphates are formed, which do not dissolve in water, but contain phosphorus available to plants [9].

Simple superphosphate is used for all crops and all soils, especially effective when used in rows. Superphosphate is non-toxic, fire and explosion resistant. Table 3 shows the physico-chemical composition of ordinary superphosphate at the phosphorus plant of Zhanazhambyl.

Table 3.

Physico-chemical composition of ordinary superphosphate at the phosphorus plant of Zhana Zhambyl

Name of indicators	Normal
Mass son of nitrogen N, %	6
Mass fraction of absorbable phosphates P ₂ O ₅ , %	26
Mass fraction of free acid H ₃ PO ₄ , %	1, 5
Mass fraction of sulfates in conversion to sulfur, %	8
Mass fraction of calcium CaO, %	12-17
Mass fraction of magnesium, %	0,5
Mass fraction of water, %	2
Granulometric composition:	
- Less than 1 mm, %	4
- From 1 to 4 mm, %	85
- Less than 6 mm, %	100
Static strength of granules, MPA (kgf/cm ²)	3 (30)
Creeps, %	100

Phosphorite flour is a long-acting pre-sowing mineral phosphorus fertilizer. Phosphorite flour is used on acidic soils, leached black soils and red soils to weaken the acidity of the soil, which is harmful to plants and microorganisms. Provides an increase in protein in grains, starch in tubers and sugar in root crops.

The content of the main macronutrients in the fertilizer: phosphorus 20%, calcium 28-32%, in

addition, for Plant Nutrition, the fertilizer contains a wide range of trace elements Fe, Zn, Mn, K, Co and the content of trace elements in phosphorus corresponds to the level of their average normal concentration in the soil [10,11].

Below, table 4 shows the physico-chemical composition of phosphorite flour at the phosphorus plant of Zhana Zhambyl.

Table 4.

Physico-chemical composition of phosphorite flour at the phosphorus plant of Zhana Zhambyl

Mineral composition, %		Chemical composition, %	
Phosphate	64	P ₂ O ₅	20 ± 1
		CaO	32,8
		MgO	1,4
Glauconite and hydrosulides	22	Fe ₂ O ₃	до 8
Quartz	7	Al ₂ O ₃	2,4
Calcite	0,7	F	2,3
Siderite	2	CO ₂	4
Pyrite and Fe hydro currents	3,5	K ₂ O + Na ₂ O	2
Gypsum and other sulfates	0,7	SiO ₂	18
Others	0,1	SO ₂	3,8
<i>Physical features</i>			
Size (mesh residue 0.18 mm), %		10	
Humidity, %		1,5	
Bulk weight, t / m ³		1,5-1,8	

Phosphorite flour is obtained by grinding previously enriched natural phosphorites. In appearance, fosmuk is a finely ground powder of dark gray color. The fertilizer has good creepiness, is not hygroscopic, does not lose its physical and chemical properties.

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